

1 **Translesion synthesis activates Xist.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 DNA polymerases are categorized based on their functions at the genomic DNA, in eukaryotes or
7 prokaryotes, and in repair and/or replication. Family Y polymerases function in the translesion synthesis
8 pathway that resolves fork structures associated with stalled replication. We studied transcriptional
9 changes resulting from impaired translesion synthesis by measuring total transcription with next
10 generation sequencing technologies in cells following acute genetic depletion of polymerase kappa (Polk)
11 and polymerase iota (Poli), the polymerases responsible for DNA replication in the context of stalled fork
12 structures that require resolving (translesion synthesis). Data supported a role for autosomal activation of
13 Xist resulting from translesion synthesis, indicating together that both repair of double strand breaks
14 (NHEJ- and HR- mediated) and translesion synthesis at stalled replication forks results in mobilization of
15 Xist non-coding RNA.
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28